

RESPONSE PAPER

LAST NAME: OGBU

FIRST NAME: SILK

PROGRAM CODE: DMCR

COURSE CODE: ACA-401D

PERIOD NUMBER: 1

INSTRUCTOR: Dr GULMA

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references.The author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 10)

List your 7 key concepts with the page number in-text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Essay Writing Basics (EUCLID 2019, 1-4)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5-13)
3. Some Rules of the Thump (EUCLID 2019, 14-16)
4. Literature Review (EUCLID 2019, 17-23)
5. Style Guide (EUCLID 2019, 24-26)
6. American Vs. British English (EUCLID 2019, 27-35)
7. Italics and Quotations (EUCLID 2019, 47-49)

BASICS OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

The decision to start a doctorate program at Euclid University was difficult for me because of two significant reasons. First, I was not sure how the online and distance learning methods would work for me. Apart from a few short meetings or courses, I have had online, my experience with formal education so far has been through face-to-face interaction with my teachers. Secondly, I was concerned about how the teaching (and/writing) style at Euclid University will differ from the techniques at the other universities I had attended in my country and how easy it will be to navigate any disparities at a doctorate level.

However, I was greatly relieved after studying the ACA-401/ACA-401D *Coursepack*: Period 1. The first thing that I noticed was that the primary academic writing style as espoused in the document is not different from what I was familiar with. The material's significant sections opened my eyes to the fine details and common errors that I should pay more attention to in my future writings. The first part of the *Coursepack* focused on the basics and essential steps of academic essay writing. Other sections highlighted issues around Plagiarism and the need for appropriate citations in a scholarly work; the

standard rules on the use of language; style; and American Vs. British English. The concluding sections of the material provided additional guidance on using the Chicago Referencing Style; and Latin abbreviations/expressions in essay writing.

In addition to the PDF document, a supplementary video provided as part of the study materials for Period 1 was quite informative. The 14-minute video started with general instructions on how to format documents in Microsoft Word and narrowed to some specific guidelines on using Euclid University's Response Paper template. Interestingly, the video provided further advice on the choice and application of either British or American English in writing Response Papers and some valuable insights on the essentials of referencing styles, rules of style, and the need to keep sentences short and simple.

In general, the study material's content speaks to the importance of understanding the standard rules in academic writing. In that sense, it provides a practical toolkit to beginners and advanced writers in search of skill-enhancing techniques.

2) ENHANCING ACADEMIC WRITING SKILLS

Although the writing of Response Papers as an approach to learning is still somewhat strange to me, I was encouraged to learn that if I follow the Coursepack guidelines, the challenges are surmountable. Therefore, the instructions on honing my academic essay writing skills, which constitute the material's central thrust, seem very helpful and insightful. Some of the concepts that stood out for me as I studied and reflected on the manual include the following:

a) Essay Writing Basics

Academic essay writing basics encompass the standard rules that should guide students embarking on an educational journey. In that regard, I found some of the content instructive. Choosing the appropriate style, language, tone, and format for writing academic papers can be an arduous task for many students. However, understanding that essay writing is an intellectual and evidence-based activity in which the writer attempts to persuade the readers about the rightness or wrongness of an idea(s) is an excellent place to start (EUCLID, 2019, 1). There are different ways of gathering and presenting evidence to support persuasive arguments, but the Coursepack offers an impressive structure that makes the task easier. I found some of the suggestions around starting early, analyzing the task, drawing up essay plans, researching the topic, making notes from readings, referencing, and editing essays relevant (EUCLID, 2019, 1–4). Finding the right balance between critical thinking and creative thinking in presenting and analyzing ideas struck me as the primary window to improving my writing. I was particularly moved by the suggestion of including pieces of evidence that not only supports my arguments but also opposes them as a way of balancing my essays and strengthening their persuasiveness (EUCLID, 2019, 2).

b) Plagiarism

Plagiarism is a matter of great concern to many students. Therefore, understanding what constitutes plagiarism and how to avoid it could help students improve their work quality and stay out of trouble. The Coursepack describes Plagiarism as “when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information” (EUCLID, 2019, 5). Therefore, to avoid Plagiarism, I must learn the rules of citation and how to give credit to the source(s) of information that I use in my work. In-text citations and List of Work Cited are sometimes tricky for me to work around because of the different referencing styles and rules guiding them. Therefore, I found the study material's suggestions very useful, particularly the tips on quotations and paraphrasing. However, I was confused by the idea that “when the information you are writing about is common knowledge that can be found in numerous areas you do not need to cite its source” (EUCLID, 2019, 10). Suppose the yardstick for measuring ‘common knowledge’ is based on the writer's assumption that the information in question can easily be found in numerous places. What happens if that assumption is wrong? In my view, ‘common knowledge’ is an exaggerated and controversial concept that requires further illumination in the study material.

c) Some Rules of the Thumb

Some rules of the thumb for writing academic papers shared in the study material are good reminders of what to keep in mind if one is desirous of avoiding significant errors. The idea of developing a thesis before writing is not new to me. However, I found the suggestion of proposing my central theory at the beginning of my work (EUCLID, 2019, 14), preferably in the very first paragraph, intriguing. After a deep reflection on this advice, I saw some of the benefits it could add to my writing, especially in clarifying my main objective. In that regard, I am looking forward to adopting it in the future.

Other exciting ideas highlighted in this section, such as keeping one's focus on the relevant aspects of the writing and avoiding sweeping generalizations not supported by evidence, are crucial to improving every academic work's quality. Perhaps, the most significant rule, in my view, is the idea that a writer must keep it simple and straightforward! Often, the temptation to impress others with our command of the English language and the extent of the vocabulary we know is difficult to resist. However, I agree that what is more important is to reduce ambiguities in our writing to enable readers to understand the message we are trying to pass on. In the future, I intend to be guided by the simple rule that “your writing should focus readers' attention on the ideas you wish to express, not on the words you have chosen to express those ideas” (EUCLID, 2019, 15). In that sense, I will start paying more attention to my choice of words, the appropriate use of paragraphs, and my sentences' length.

Some rules suggest the use of minimal quotations, balanced arguments, diligent proofreading, etc., which resonated with me. I agree that the necessity of rigorous proofreading to improve one's writing quality cannot be over-emphasized. Indeed, the advice that “when you finish writing, read your paper out loud... writing that does not sound

right will not read right” (EUCLID, 2019, 16) may sound funny, but it makes a lot of sense. I tried it. It was a hilarious experience, but I learned something new.

d) Literature Review

The literature review section of the study material dwelled mainly on grammar and the rules guiding punctuations, verbs, pronouns, conjunctions, etc., in writing. In the beginning, this section provided 11 'reminders' on the proper use of grammar that writers should keep in mind (EUCLID, 2019, 17–18). Unfortunately, the reminders did not include examples of the rules' wrong and right applications, which did not make them easy to understand or remember. Without clear illustrations, the 11 reminders created more problems for me that they may have hoped to solve because I was more confused at the end than before I read them.

Nonetheless, it was interesting for me that this section shed some light on the confusion around using possessive pronouns and contractions – such as ‘your’ and ‘you’re’- in writing and the errors associated with them. My great takeaway was the suggestion to pay particular attention to punctuations, especially the use of coma in my sentences. The idea of including the final coma in sentences has never struck me as capable of making much of a difference, but after giving it some thought, I am inclined to agree with the view that:

This approach is efficient in that the INCLUSION of the final comma will never increase ambiguity in a sentence, while the EXCLUSION of the comma sometimes will. Likewise, the EXCLUSION of the comma will never increase the effectiveness of a sentence, while INCLUSION often will (EUCLID, 2019, 20).

In a way, I can now see how the inclusion of the final coma and the effective use of punctuations, in general, can tremendously improve the clarity of sentences and the quality of my writing.

e) American Vs. British English

For many years now, the greatest source of confusion for me about speaking and writing in the English language are the differences between American and British English and where, when, and how I should use them appropriately. Although most of my formal education took place in Nigeria - a former colony of Britain – where British English was used for learning instructions, I have become more exposed to American English through my work, recent training, and social interactions. I have often wondered if American English is an adulteration of British English, which is regarded as the authentic version by many teachers of the language in my country that I know. Somehow, I have been reluctant to use American English in official communication and formal writings to avoid trouble. However, I have watched the growing influence of American English in Nigeria and across the world with some level of amazement. The Coursepack attributes this trend to the following reasons:

1. Population: US vs. UK (SAE/SBE ca 70% vs. 17% of all native English)
2. Wealth of the US economy vs. the UK, and influences
3. The magnitude of higher education in America vs. the UK.
4. The magnitude of the publishing industry in America
5. Magnitude of global mass media and media technology influence
6. The appeal of American popular culture on language and habits
7. The international political and economic position of the US (EUCLID, 2019, 27)

Indeed, many of the factors outlined above make sense and have helped explain the increasing dominance of American English today. Nevertheless, some students' primary concern about mixing up the two variants of the language in academic writing may remain for several reasons. Some of them include the confusion arising from the following differences and commonalities between the Standard American English (SAE) and the Standard British English (SBE):

- Different Pronunciation, Although Same Spelling (EUCLID, 2019, 27–28);
- Different Spelling, Although Same Pronunciation (EUCLID, 2019, 28);
- Same Term, Different but Similar Spelling and Pronunciation (EUCLID, 2019, 28);
- Same Words, But Different or Additional Meanings (EUCLID, 2019, 28–29); and
- Differences in Grammar, Syntax, Punctuation, General Usage (EUCLID, 2019, 29–35).

Although I now understand that it is okay to use either the SAE or SBE as long as I am consistent with the choice that I made and do not mix them up in a single document, I am still unsure how to navigate through that maze on my own. Therefore, I am grateful for the grammar-check software (Grammarly) gift from Euclid University, which could assist me in this regard. Hopefully, the number of my grey hairs will not increase over this issue.

3) CONCLUSION

From my interactions with the ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1, I can say that I have learned a lot about writing academic papers generally and writing Response Papers at Euclid University, in particular. Although I am familiar with some of the

document's information, a lot of them were surprisingly new to me. Either way, I found the reminders and the new concepts both helpful and instructive.

As I embark on this new academic journey at Euclid University, the study materials for Period 1 have given me a new momentum. I am looking forward to implementing some of the suggestions around essay writing basics, citations, rules of style, Standard American English Vs. Standard British English and Latin abbreviations, among others. I am already practicing some of the video's instructions around using Euclid University's RP template, referencing styles, and punctuations. While the destination may still be far ahead, these study materials have encouraged me to take the first step.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.